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Enhancing Healthcare Data Confidentiality through Fragmentation Techniques within Cloud-enabled Intelligent IoT Security and Privacy Frameworks

Andreas Andreou¹[0000-0002-9432-916X], Constandinos X. Mavromoustakis²[0000-0003-0333-8034], Evangelos Markakis³[0000-0003-0959-598X], Athina Bourdena⁴[0000-0002-1081-2868] and George Mastorakis⁵[0000-0002-6733-5652]

¹ University of Nicosia, Nicosia, Cyprus, andreou.andreas@unic.ac.cy

² University of Nicosia, Nicosia, Cyprus, mavromoustakis.c@unic.ac.cy

³ Hellenic Mediterranean University, Heraklion, Crete, Greece, markakis@pasiphae.eu

⁴ Hellenic Mediterranean University, Heraklion, Crete, Greece, bourdena@hmu.gr

⁵ Hellenic Mediterranean University Agios Nikolaos, Crete, Greece, gmastorakis@hmu.gr

Abstract. In the context of the Internet of Things (IoT) era, securing and privatizing IoT-enabled healthcare systems present significant challenges, particularly in ensuring the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of health data exchange. This study explores data fragmentation and employs polynomial and Newton-Gregory's divided difference interpolation techniques for encrypting sensitive health information, such as patient IDs, to enhance data security and utility. The research aims to improve data integrity and ensure end-user availability by fragmenting data. The performance of this methodology is thoroughly evaluated against modern techniques, showing notable superiority in precision, recall, and F_1 -score across different correlation index values. Moreover, the study's analysis of time complexity for overhead tasks highlights its efficiency compared to existing technologies. By emphasizing the need for collective efforts in addressing security and privacy concerns, this research contributes to building trust and encouraging the adoption of sophisticated healthcare technologies, paving the way for a secure, data-driven healthcare future.

Keywords: fragmentation, data exchange, healthcare, encryption, cloud repository.

1 Introduction

The healthcare sector, responsible for managing extensive sensitive data, including medical histories and personal details, places utmost importance on securing this information to protect patient privacy and counter cyber threats. Healthcare data exchange, vital for quality care delivery, enables information-sharing among trusted entities, is crucial in emergencies for timely decision-making, and improves patient outcomes [1]. It also reduces redundant medical testing, easing patient transitions between care providers and contributing to a more efficient healthcare system [2]. The rise of global

mobility accentuates the need for an interconnected health system, allowing individuals, especially those with chronic conditions, to access their health records anywhere, ensuring continuous care [3].

This backdrop highlights cloud computing's role in ensuring data sovereignty and confidentiality through a novel data-sharing framework based on data fragmentation and encryption [4]. This method obscures sensitive data across cloud storages, maintaining privacy and utility while enabling data reassembly through advanced interpolation techniques [5]. The proposed database fragmentation enhances query efficiency and security, ensuring that isolated data fragments cannot lead to privacy breaches. The model employs a Virtual Private Network (VPN) for secure data transfers, overcoming geographical limitations and censorship, and ensuring data's secure retrieval and availability [6]. This holistic approach addresses healthcare data security and privacy challenges, laying the foundation for a safe, efficient, and patient-focused healthcare information exchange ecosystem [7].

Fig. 1 elaborately showcases the architecture of an end user's gateway server, detailing its integration with a Virtual Private Gateway (VPG) within a Virtual Private Cloud (VPC), forming a VPN. This VPN, depicted as a secure communication tunnel, emphasizes private, IP-based interactions across various VPCs in a public cloud, illustrating the system's extensive data exchange capabilities. The figure highlights the relationship between user attributes and confidentiality constraints to ensure unique data handling per Service Level Agreements (SLA) [8]. It also introduces the Singleton pattern, which aids in maintaining a unique occurrence of critical attributes, thus enhancing global data access [9]. The model effectively segments datasets into distinct confidentiality requirements (CR), aligning with user specifications and SLA, and encrypts them for storage across different cloud repositories. This setup underscores the importance of secure data management. Additionally, the figure depicts a data reconstruction phase where a DataBase Management System (DBMS) processes and reassembles the data fragments, ensuring safe and efficient data retrieval for end users [10]. This illustration underscores the complex mechanisms essential for upholding data privacy, security, and accessibility within the network.

Fig. 1. System Architecture

1.1 Motivation

The healthcare sector's shift towards digitalization underscores the urgent need for a secure, globally accessible health and care cloud repository to enhance medical data interoperability and facilitate collaborations across healthcare providers, researchers, and patients [11]. However, establishing such a repository presents significant data security and privacy challenges. This study explores advanced encryption techniques and stringent security measures to ensure the safe, cross-border exchange of sensitive health information, addressing pivotal data security challenges [12]. Through these cryptographic efforts, the research aims to create a digital health ecosystem that is both secure and universally accessible, significantly advancing global healthcare integration and effectiveness.

1.2 Contribution & Novelty

This study introduces an innovative cryptographic approach focused on data fragmentation to bolster the security of sensitive information exchanges within cloud and IoT networks. Dispersing data fragments across cloud repositories conceals crucial data values, enhancing security. This method ensures secure data handling in healthcare systems by utilizing Newton-Gregory's divided difference interpolation for decryption and reassembly [13]. The technique protects patient confidentiality effectively and simplifies encryption processes without compromising complexity. This advancement significantly reduces unauthorized access risks, demanding precise fragment retrieval for data reconstruction [14]. It represents a crucial step in strengthening data privacy and security, contributing to a more interconnected and secure digital health landscape.

2 System Model

This research enhances data privacy and confidentiality in data exchange by introducing a dynamic method for fragment reconstruction using Newton-Gregory's divided differences and interpolation techniques. Distributing critical attributes and employing a carefully crafted decryption method aims to maintain the confidentiality of sensitive data while ensuring database utility. This approach reflects a dedication to developing advanced encryption mechanisms that safeguard data integrity and promote accessibility within secure boundaries.

2.1 Preliminaries

Definition 1: Confidential Constraints in Data Fragmentation

Confidential constraints in data fragmentation involve dividing and distributing sensitive information across multiple storage locations on servers with limited communication to boost security and reduce unauthorized access risks [15]. Defined as $c \subseteq A$, where A encompasses all attributes under consideration, this method systematically

segments sensitive attributes, safeguarding data confidentiality and integrity in line with strict data protection standards.

Definition 2: Uniqueness of Confidential Constraints

In the realm of data security, confidential constraints $C = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n\}$, represent distinct partitions of sensitive data attributes, each uniquely designed for secure storage and handling. Ensuring no confidential constraint c_i is subsumed by another c_j , this framework mandates that $c_i, c_j \in C, \forall i \neq j$, reinforcing the uniqueness and non-overlapping nature of each constraint. This approach is crucial for eliminating redundancy and providing robust, comprehensive protection of sensitive data segments, thus enhancing the privacy and security of the information management system.

Definition 3: Dataset Utility and Attribute Weighting

Dataset utility is defined by selecting a critical subset of attributes u from a larger set A , where $u \subseteq A$, focusing on those essential for the dataset's operational effectiveness. Attributes within u are quantitatively evaluated and prioritized using a weighting function $w(u)$, which assigns values based on their contribution to overall utility. This process supports optimized data management by highlighting and prioritizing the most valuable attributes, ensuring the dataset's integrity and efficiency.

Lemma 1: Constraint Compliance of Individual Fragments Through Fragmentation

In data fragmentation, individual fragments F and confidential constraints C are established to protect sensitive information. Each fragment f complies with these constraints, ensuring no fragment alone contains sufficient data to breach any constraint $c \notin f$. It provides sensitive data is distributed across fragments, enhancing security by preventing unauthorized data reconstruction or misuse and maintaining privacy by design.

Lemma 2: Attribute Coverage by Data Fragments

Data fragmentation ensures that attributes distributed across all fragments comprehensively cover every relationship r within the relational framework R , guaranteeing no property is missed or underrepresented. This approach disperses sensitive attributes for enhanced security and maintains the dataset's integrity by ensuring that all defined relationships and properties are fully embodied within the fragmented data.

Lemma 3: Uniqueness of Attributes Across Fragments

In data fragmentation, each fragment contains a unique set of attributes, ensuring no overlap or redundancy among fragments F . This principle is mathematically confirmed as $\forall f_i, f_j \in F, i \neq j \implies f_i \cap f_j = \emptyset$, emphasizing a core design aspect for improving data security and integrity. The uniqueness of attributes in each fragment simplifies data management and enhances control over data access and manipulation across distributed systems.

2.2 Proposed Framework

Enhancing data security through refined dataset fragmentation in distributed systems is essential for adhering to specific correlation constraints, utilizing a singleton design pattern for precise constraint management and partitioning. This system enables dataset reconstruction with a subset of $k \leq n$ attributes and an encryption key, preventing adversaries from accessing complete information with fewer attributes. By dividing the dataset into k fragments based on polynomial (1) coefficients, where a_0 encodes sensitive data like patient IDs, this approach ensures secure and structured data handling, safeguarding against unauthorized data reconstruction.

$$P(x) = a_0 + a_1x + a_2x^2 + \dots + a_{k-1}x^{k-1} \quad (1)$$

The encryption key $x = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ comprises the coefficients of this polynomial. The application of Newton-Gregory's divided difference interpolation enhances the ability to derive the coefficients and, by extension, the sensitive constant value from the set of pairs $(x_i, P(x_i))$, for $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$, as represented in equation (2)

$$P(x) = P(x_{k-1}) + \Delta_{P(x_{k-1})}(x - x_{k-1}) + \Delta_{\Delta P(x_{k-1})}^2(x - x_{k-1})(x - x_k) \\ + \dots + \Delta_{\Delta^{n-k-2}P(x_{k-1})}^{n-k-1} \prod_{i=k-1}^n (x - x_i) \quad (2)$$

Here, $\Delta_{P(x_{k-1})}, \Delta_{\Delta P(x_{k-1})}^2, \dots, \Delta_{\Delta^{n-k-2}P(x_{k-1})}^{n-k-1}$ denote the 1st through $(n - k - 1)^{th}$ divided differences, respectively.

The algorithm encrypts essential attributes, integrating them into the dataset before distributing the fragments to different repositories, adhering to confidentiality constraints. It ensures fragments with shared sensitive attributes are not co-located, enhancing data security and privacy.

Algorithm 1 takes a comprehensive approach to fragmenting and encrypting sensitive data while respecting confidentiality constraints. By assigning encrypted fragments to repositories in a manner that ensures compliance with security protocols, the algorithm enhances data privacy and integrity.

3 Paradigm

The proposed model innovatively combines cryptographic techniques, data fragmentation, and distributed storage strategies to bolster the security, privacy, and accessibility of sensitive information within digital ecosystems. It employs a sophisticated, multi-layered approach to address the challenges of data security and management effectively. The model defines a set of essential attributes (e.g., ID, Name, Surname, Date of Birth) for practical demonstration, governed by specific constraints to prevent the combination of sensitive attributes that could jeopardize data confidentiality (e.g., Name cannot be paired with Telephone in one fragment). These regulations ensure that the dataset maintains integrity and privacy, prohibiting attribute combinations within fragments that violate confidentiality constraints, thus striking a crucial balance between ensuring data utility and protecting privacy in data management practices.

Algorithm 1: Fragmentation**Input:**

1. A : Set of Attributes
2. C : Set of Confidential Constraints
3. n : Number of Fragments to be created

Output:

4. Allocation of Encrypted Data Fragments to designated repositories
5. Begin with the set of attributes A and constraints C
6. Generate n fragments from the attributes set A , considering the constraints C
7. Define a set of repositories $R = \{r_1, r_2, \dots, r_m\}$ where each fragment will be allocated
8. **For** $i = 1$ to n **do** \\\for each fragment
9. **For** $j=1$ to m **do** \\\for each constraint
10. Ensure individual fragments satisfy the constraints C
11. Assign fragments to specific repositories from the set R
12. **End for**
13. **End for**
14. **For** $f \in r_k$ **do**
15. **If** $c_k < 1$ **then**
16. $f \leftarrow a_s$ \\\encrypt sensitive attribute
17. Assign encrypted attributes to the corresponding fragment
18. **End if**
19. **End for**
20. **If** $f = \{a \in c_k | c_k > 1\}$ **then**
21. $r_k \leftarrow f_k - a$ \\\Exclude the attribute a from the fragment f_k in case it violates any constraint
22. **End if**
23. **For** $f \in r_k$ **do**
24. **If** $f \cap f_l = \emptyset$ in repository r_l and $(f, f_l) \notin U, \forall f_l \in r_l$ **then**
25. $f: r_l \leftarrow r_l \cup f$ \\\Update repository r_l by adding fragment
26. Store the fragment in the repository, ensuring that it is mutually exclusive with existing fragments
27. **End if**
28. **End for**

The polynomial (3) interprets the fragments stored in three cloud repositories.

$$P(x) = a_0 + a_1x + a_2x^2 \quad (3)$$

In the proposed encryption schema, the ID assigned to each patient is denoted by the constant a_0 , which holds the position of the most sensitive piece of information within the dataset. This constant forms the basis for a cryptographic approach where the coefficients for x^2 and x are selected through a stochastic process, leading to the formulation of a key vector x_i , with i ranging from 1 to 3.

Upon determining the values of the key vector, specified as $\{x = 1, x = 2, x = 4\}$, these values are substituted into predetermined second-degree polynomials. These polynomials utilize the patient's ID (represented by a_0) as the constant term, facilitating

the generation of encrypted *ID* values. The resultant encrypted *IDs* are then integrated into Table 1, populating the last three columns dedicated to showcasing these encrypted identifiers.

The encryption method results in three distinct dataset fragments, each containing encrypted patient *IDs* alongside specific attributes: names and birthdates, surnames and phone numbers, and diseases with nationalities. Despite encryption, the dataset is structured with constraints to enhance privacy and security, indicating that disclosing two attributes could decrypt and expose patient information. This approach protects patient *IDs* and organizes data into secure, privacy-compliant fragments.

Table 1. Generating values for fragments

ID	Polynomial P(x)	x=1 CR ₁	x=2 CR ₂	x=4 CR ₃
578930	1x ² +7x+578930	578938	578948	578930
426591	2x ² +3x+426591	426596	426605	426635
643293	5x ² +2x+643293	643300	643317	643381
649322	6x ² +1x+649322	649329	649347	649422

Through a dual-authentication process, authorized entities can decrypt patient data, significantly bolstering security. This process relies on possessing a key vector x_i , where $i = 1,2,3$ initially used for encrypting patient *IDs* and accessing encrypted *ID* values. The identified constant based on the calculations from Table 2 generates the constant $a_0 = 426591$ represents a patient's original *ID*, enabling trusted parties to query the system effectively and extract detailed patient information, thus facilitating access to comprehensive patient records as needed.

Table 2. Newton-Gregory's Divided Difference Interpolation

i	x_i	$P(x_i)$	$\Delta_{P(x_i)}$	$\Delta_{\Delta P(x_i)}^2$
1	1	426596	$\frac{P(x_2) - P(x_1)}{x_2 - x_1} = 9$	$\frac{\Delta_{P(x_2)} - \Delta_{P(x_1)}}{x_3 - x_1} = 2$
2	2	426605		
3	4	426635	$\frac{P(x_3) - P(x_2)}{x_3 - x_2} = 15$	

4 Results Appraisal

This study emphasizes the importance of Confidentiality, Integrity, and Availability (CIA) in healthcare data security, introducing a novel encryption method using polynomial and Newton-Gregory interpolation. It ensures data confidentiality, maintains

integrity through fragmentation, and enhances accessibility, aligning with the CIA triad. Comparative analysis reveals in Fig. 2 this method's time efficiency and superiority over existing approaches, demonstrating its robustness and scalability for secure healthcare data management.

Fig. 3 illustrates the evolution of Precision, Recall, and F1-Score metrics across various gamma (γ) values ranging from 0 to 1. Precision consistently remains high, generally hovering around 0.95 to 1.00, indicating that the model maintains a strong ability to identify relevant instances accurately, although with some fluctuations. Recall shows greater variability, ranging from approximately 0.82 to 0.88, suggesting that the model's ability to capture all relevant instances fluctuates more significantly as γ changes. The F1-Score, which balances precision and recall, remains relatively stable around 0.90 but exhibits peaks and troughs corresponding to the changes in recall. Notably, the highest precision does not coincide with the highest recall, highlighting a trade-off between these metrics. The F1-Score generally follows the trends in recall, given the latter's influence on the harmonic mean, reflecting the model's overall performance as γ varies. These trends underscore the model's adaptability and the delicate balance between minimizing false positives (precision) and maximizing true positives (recall) as γ is adjusted.

Fig. 2. Efficiency Analysis of Overhead Task Processing Time

Fig. 3. Evaluation of Precision, Recall, and F_1 -Score across $\gamma \in [0,1]$

5 Conclusion and Future Work

Healthcare data exchange crucially enhances patient outcomes and service efficiency, facing challenges like standardization and stringent security needs. Despite these, progress is achievable, with growing importance alongside technological advancements. A comparative study reveals the proposed model matches the optimal Privacy Threshold Scheme's performance but with less complexity, highlighting its superior efficiency and robustness as an advanced solution in healthcare data management.

Future efforts will focus on refining data security's core principles—confidentiality, integrity, and availability—within healthcare systems. The goal is to boost the proposed scheme's effectiveness by lowering computational complexity for large-scale, cross-border healthcare data exchanges. This commitment aims to meet the growing demands of global healthcare infrastructures with secure, efficient data exchange solutions.

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